

IMPROVING THE PERFORMANCE OF THE FUEL INJECTION SYSTEM

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Annotation. This article provides information on the advantages and disadvantages of the injector fuel supply system, drawings and operating characteristics of the multi-branch injection system, the principles of operation.

Key words: injector, multi-line spraying system, fuel tank, filter, fuel pump, main fuel line, pressure regulator, distribution pipe.

Nowadays, every new car is an injector. Although they are more expensive to maintain than carburetor machines, in recent years computerized sensor injector systems have demonstrated sufficient sensitivity, accuracy, and precision. They justify their high cost with good performance, high fuel economy, cleaner emissions and higher power. Some car models even burn 95-100%. Thanks to innovations in the design, the systems are constantly being improved, and the cost is becoming cheaper. The refueling system is not as new as some people think. For example, the 1957 Chevrolet Corvette is equipped with a fuel injection system. These early injector engines used mechanical injectors (also called injectors) [1,2,3]. They appeared as spring-loaded plate valves. In such engines, when the fuel pressure reaches the level given in the mechanical injectors, the injector is opened and the fuel is sprayed into the inlet manifold to mix with the air in the combustion chamber path.[4] Modern engines use computer-controlled electronic injectors. A transistor connects an injector to a computer (also called an injector driver) and in this case it connects the circuit. This allows current to flow through the solenoid (coil) in the injector. [5]

An injector is a mechanism that supplies fuel to the combustion chamber.

Photo 1. Injector view

1-fuel tank, 2-coarse filter, 3-fuel pump, 4-main fuel line, 5-fine filter, 6-pressure regulator, 7-distribution pipe, 8- nozzle, 9 injectors, 10 fuel return path.

Multi-injector fuel injection

Multi-injector fuel injection is a carburetor-free system that mixes fuel directly with the air in the car's throttle without spraying it into each cylinder of the individual injectors (Figure 1). These systems are simpler and usually cheaper than multi-point fuel injection systems. Some of these systems use solenoids (coils) to inject fuel into the air.[6,7]

Fig

The principle of operation of a multi-point spray system.

- An electric fuel pump pumps fuel into the throttle body. The throttle body is similar to a carburetor and includes an injector and a fuel pressure regulator.
- The fuel pressure regulator maintains the required pressure in the fuel and returns the unused fuel to the fuel tank.[8]
- The engine control unit controls the operation of one or two injectors located inside the throttle body. It reduces the electric current (by adjusting the pulse length) to the injector solenoid for a certain period of time, the fuel is sprayed under pressure, mixed with air, and passes through the throttle on the way to the engine.

Multi-point fuel injection is another type of carburetor-free system.

The principle of operation of a multi-point spray system.

1. An electric fuel pump injects fuel into the fuel rail with injectors attached. The fuel rail may also have a fuel pressure regulator. It is designed to maintain the required pressure in the fuel and return the unused fuel to the fuel tank. The injectors on each cylinder are mounted on one side to the fuel rail and on the other side to the engine inlet.
2. The control unit transmits a pulse of a certain length to the injector solenoid and the fuel is transferred under pressure to the inlet valve in front of the inlet valve.[9,10]

Internal combustion engines with injector supply system are very common and have the **following advantages;**

- The advantages of the electronic system also allow you to understand how the injector differs from the carburetor. The power of injector engines is much higher than that of carburetor engines.[11,12]
- the positioning angle can be precisely set in the system and the gasoline injection is measured according to the number of revolutions. The injector can only operate stably with high quality fuel. This releases less toxic substances into the atmosphere.
- mixing of fuel and air mixture, ensuring fuel supply in accordance with the amount of air supplied;[13,14]
- **Disadvantages of injectors:**
 - complex diagnostic process;
 - fuel sensitivity;
 - high cost of repairs and spare parts.
- The electronic engine allows you to increase the power of the car, but if it does not work, you will need to take the car to a service station for diagnosis and repair.

On any injection engine, sensors are installed that receive information about:

- coolant temperature;
- vehicle speed;
- detonation processes in the engine;
- the position of the crankshaft and the frequency of its rotation;

- electrical voltage in the on-board network;
- air consumption;
- damper position.[15]

Conclusion

1. The design (Drawing) of the multi-injection injector supply system has been developed.
2. The advantages and disadvantages of the injector engine supply system are explained.
3. The multi-branch spray system is illuminated.
4. Development suggestions and recommendations were made[16]

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